

Visual problems in Students of Schools under the School Health Program and Others

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Abstract:

Visual problem in school children is a globally important public health issue. An emerging important cause of visual impairment is uncorrected refractive errors, which if not detected and corrected in time, can harm a child's physical, cognitive, and psychosocial development. A school-based comparative cross-sectional study was conducted from January to December, 2019 to see the pattern and prevalence of visual problems in a representative sample of children attending classes 1 to 5 of selected primary schools under the School Health Program (SHP) and non-SHP schools of Dhaka and Chittagong. 277 school children, aged 5-13 years, and their guardians were interviewed for approximately 30-40 minutes each with a pretested semi-structured questionnaire and checklist. Visual problems were categorized as diminished visual acuity and presence of other ocular morbidities. It was found that diminished vision was more common in non-SHP students. Chi Square was done to see the association between the variables, and they were found to be not significant ($p > 0.05$). The proportion of diminished vision was found higher among respondents with age group below 10 years ($X^2 = 0.16$, $p = 0.901$), more propensity towards males ($X^2 = 0.751$, $p = 0.386$), Islam religion ($X^2 = 0.966$, $p = 0.326$), nuclear family ($X^2 = 0.495$, $p = 0.482$), most of which was not significant. This study revealed that ocular morbidity was weakly associated with malnourished non-SHP students ($X^2 = 4.556$, $p = 0.033$). Lack of understanding and awareness of the consequences and the severity of the ocular morbidities seemed to be the main reason behind the delay in seeking treatment. The study findings may be utilized for further planning and evaluation of the existing school health services, for further improvement and implementation of SHP in all schools, and for conducting an appropriate intervention programs to reduce this preventable problem.

Keywords: *refractive error, school health program, visual acuity, ocular morbidity, semi structured questionnaire*

JSR

Accepted 20 April 2021
Published 25 April 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4718485

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Introduction

School age is essential for detecting ocular morbidity as childhood is a sensitive period for the development of the visual system and children have longer life expectancy than adults, so any ocular disorder that remains untreated during this period can lead to visual impairment or blindness. These visual impairments or blindness may affect an individual's health, educational achievement, employment options, and social functioning across lifespan (Uddin, 2017). Assessment of visual problems in children is important because while some eye conditions cause ocular morbidity, others invariably lead to blindness. Moreover, while some conditions such as refractive errors and cataract are treatable, others like measles and vitamin A deficiency are largely preventable (Kumah, 2015). Therefore, when a problem is diagnosed, it can be treated or a solution is found to prevent further deterioration of sight. The Childhood Blindness Study in Bangladesh revealed that 31% of the blindness was due to problems with the lens (cataract), and 27% of the blindness was due to problems in the cornea (Vitamin A deficiency). Including glaucoma (4%) and aphakia (5%), 67% of childhood blindness is thus avoidable (preventable or treatable). The study also found that 90% of childhood blindness was developed within the first 5 years of life. The study indicated that an estimated 40,000 children are blind in Bangladesh.

The magnitude of eye diseases and the importance of ocular health among children have been estimated by many ocular morbidity surveys. In Nigeria, a study conducted on 286 children showed the leading causes of childhood eye morbidity are refractive error (25.7%), vernal conjunctivitis (25.3%), eye injury (13.3%), and corneal inflammation (12.5%) (Salman, 2010). Uncorrected refractive error is one of the most important/common causes of visual impairment around the world and the second leading cause of treatable blindness (Dandona, 2002). To address the issue of blindness in children, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched a global initiative, VISION 2020 – The Right to Sight, to eliminate avoidable blindness among children (Hashim, 2008). To achieve the goal of Vision 2020, refractive error has been considered as one of the priority eye diseases in Bangladesh National Eye Care Plan (Muhit, 2012). Vision 2020 –the Right to Sight, was launched by the World Health Organization (WHO) and International Agency for Prevention of Blindness (IAPB) in 1999 in Beijing to eliminate avoidable blindness by the year 2020. The Government of Bangladesh is one of the signatories of Vision 2020. In 2005, National Eye Care (NEC) plan was developed along with a separate operational plan of Health Nutrition & Population Sector Program (HNPS) which was subsequently incorporated into the new Health, Population, Nutrition Development Sector Program (HPNDSP).

Vision screening must focus on pre-school children if the aim of the screening is to detect and treat conditions that may lead to amblyopia, whereas if the aim is to detect and correct significant refractive errors (not likely to lead to amblyopia) then refractive (and color vision) screening at 5-6 years of age should be done. Myopia is the refractive error most likely to develop during primary school, presenting typically between 8 and 12 years of age, thus screening for entry to secondary school is warranted (Logan, 2004). Visual problems significantly affect a child's ability to participate and learn at school. A child must be healthy to learn and a child must learn to be healthy. School Health Program is one through which children can be screened for various health risks including visual problems that lead to decreased visual acuity such as refractive errors, strabismus, amblyopia, and trachoma (Uddin, 2017)

The School is an ideal setting for health promotion activities and the school system can be the most efficient and organized way to reach a large portion of the population including young people, their family members, and neighbors.

The Bangladesh government has identified the schools to be focal points to provide necessary health care facilities to young citizens, the future of the country. The School Health Program was started in 1972 with 23 clinics all over the country; it is a wing of Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS) under Primary Health Care (PHC) where services are provided through the school system to improve the health and well-being of children and in some cases whole families and the broader community. As a result, a large number of children will be covered by health services that will reduce the total morbidity rate and burden to the family and community thereby. Vision screening is done by a Medical officer under the School Health Program (SHP), to identify visual and other eye problems which may be preventing children from seeing the blackboard and following classes. Reliable, valid, and up-to-date data on the magnitude of visual problems in school going children is essential for planning and improvement of the services of the School Health Program. This study will provide insight into the effectiveness of the school health program in visual screening of students and the findings can be used not only to reduce the prevalence of ocular morbidity in children but also help to raise awareness among people and help the concerned authorities to initiate plans to compulsorily incorporate programs in the schools of our country.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out to see if there is any significant difference between the visual problems occurring in students of schools under the School Health Program and other schools that are not under the School Health program.

Study design

A school-based cross-sectional comparative study was conducted to compare the prevalence of visual problems occurring in students of schools under the School Health Program and those that are not.

Study place

The study was carried out in four primary schools of Dhaka and Chittagong. The two schools that are under the School Health Program were Bagmonirum A.S. Government Primary School, Dampara, Chittagong and Hazi Gani Government Primary School, Azimpur, Dhaka. The two nonprogram schools were CDA Shishu Kanon School, Mehdibag, Chittagong, and Nilkhet Government Primary School, Dhaka.

Study period

The study occurred over a period of one year, from 1st January to 31st December 2019. During the initial period, the topic was selected and after extensive literature reviewing, the protocol was developed, presented and approved by May 2019. Research instrument development and pretesting of the questionnaire was completed by August 2019. Data collection and entry data was done from September to mid-November 2019. Data processing and analysis along with report writing was completed by December 2019 and then finished with the final report submission. Literature review which was continued throughout the study period until submission of the report.

Study population

The study population included the students of two primary schools under the School Health Program and two non-program schools of Dhaka and Chittagong cities of Bangladesh.

Selection criteria**Inclusion criteria:**

- All Students of class 1 to class 5
- Both boys and girls
- Children with parents' consent who are willing to participate

Exclusion criteria: Students with the following conditions will be excluded from the study

- Students suffering from major eye problems
- Students suffering from chronic illnesses
- Students with any physical disability
- Students with any mental handicap

Sample size

To estimate the sample size for two-sample situations, the following formula was used for this study:

$$n = z^2V/d^2$$

Where,

n = the desired sample size

z = the standard normal deviate at 95% confidence level = 1.96

V = intermediate value

d = acceptable error = 7% = 0.07

$$\text{and, } V = P_1 (1-P_1) + P_2 (1-P_2)$$

P_1 = prevalence of visual problems (refractive errors) in students of schools under the School Health Program

P_2 = prevalence of visual problems (refractive errors) in students of schools that are not under the School Health Program

In a previous school-based study done in Bangladesh (Rahman MM, 2014), the prevalence of visual problems (refractive error) in school children was found to be 9.5% ($p = 0.095$), which has been used for both P_1 and P_2 , as separate data was not available for students of schools under the School Health Program.

Therefore, $V = \{0.095 (1 - 0.095) + 0.095 (1 - 0.095)\} = 0.172$

By considering the 10% nonresponse rate, sample size (n) = $(135 + 13.5) = 148.5$ for each group (students under program school and non-program schools).

Thus, a total sample size (n) of 297 was calculated, although 277 students could finally be enrolled in the study.

Research approach

The research proposal was presented at first in front of the honorable faculty members of the Department of Epidemiology and then to the faculty members of National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM). Research Proposal was approved after a thorough discussion. Based on their valuable comments and suggestions during the discussion, necessary modifications were made and the proposal was submitted to the Ethical Review Committee of NIPSOM for approval. Research proposals with ethical approval letters, research instruments, consent, and assent forms were shown to the

Program Manager of the School Health program, Civil Surgeons in Dhaka and Chittagong, Medical Officers of the School Health Clinics of Azimpur, Dhaka, and Chittagong and Headmistresses of the respective study schools for the permission of data collection. After receiving permission from the respective authorities, the researcher briefly described her identity and explained the purpose of the study to the participants and their guardians, so that the respondents could understand the question and respond accordingly. Informed written consent and assent of the respondents and their guardians were signed by them before data collection, ensuring privacy and confidentiality. The queries of the participants or guardians were answered by the researcher during the data collection period. Finally, the respondents were thanked for their participation and cooperation in the study.

Sampling technique

Stratified sampling technique was used to select the study samples. At first, two out of 23 School Health Clinics (SHC) were randomly selected from a list obtained from the Program Manager of the 'Adolescent and School Health Program', DGHS, Mohakhali, Dhaka. They were the School Health Clinics of Dhaka (Azimpur) and Chittagong. Then, from the two School Health Clinics, the list of schools under the School Health Program (SHP) was collected, from which a school under each of the two School Health Clinics was conveniently selected. Two non-SHP schools were selected nearby to program schools to maintain the similarity of social background. In each of the four primary schools, the students were stratified according to the class they studied in class 1 to class 5, and from each class (or stratum) a separate and independent sample was randomly selected by proportional allocation. Subjects were interviewed considering the availability of their guardians and their willingness to participate, and those who fulfilled the selection criteria were taken as samples. Participants who didn't fulfil the criteria were not included. Thus, 277 samples were achieved within the time limit of data collection.

Data collection instruments

Data collection instruments included a pretested semi structured questionnaire and an observation checklist. The questionnaire was developed using selected variables according to the specific objectives based on literature review. The English questionnaire and checklist was drafted first and completed after thorough checking and appropriate alterations. It was translated into Bengali for data collection, which was then retranslated to check if the original meaning was retained. Small modifications to the wording of some items were made to ensure local understanding based on pretesting of the Bengali version with 6 students of other schools. After problem identification, necessary corrections were made and the research instrument was finalized. Students on whom pretesting was done were not taken as study participants. The questionnaire included questions related to the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of the students and their family. Information regarding the schools under study, vaccination and deworming status of the students, history of breastfeeding, family history of visual problems, etc., was also taken. Questions regarding the lifestyle of the participants including the intake of Vitamin A containing food, eye straining activity, history, and symptoms of eye problems were asked. The checklist was used to record the findings of the clinical data, i.e., visual acuity, color vision assessment, basic ophthalmic examination, height, and weight of the student.

Data collection tools

Data collection tools included Snellen chart, Ishihara color plates, pen torch, weighing scale, and a measuring tape. The same tools were used for the respondents of the schools to prevent any instrument bias. For the basic ophthalmic examination, a standard Snellen Chart with the Bengali alphabet was used to measure the visual acuity of the students, Ishihara Color Plates were used to test their color vision, a pen torch to test the reflexes and

to assess other visual problems. Height was measured by a measuring tape calibrated in centimeters and weight was measured by Miyako analog weight scale.

Data collection techniques

Data collection techniques included face-to-face interviews with the guardian from which information about socio-demographic and economic characteristics, lifestyle, dietary patterns, vaccination, Vitamin A supplementation, history of any visual problems, injury or operations of the student was collected by a semi structured questionnaire. Observation checklist included the measurement of height, weight, visual acuity, color vision test, and basic ophthalmic assessment of the student. Available medical records regarding his/her visual problems were reviewed. All above were done, collected and recorded by the researcher herself from the respondents, during the school hours. Around 30 – 40 mins were required to interview each student and their guardian. Privacy was maintained during the interview as far as possible.

Visual acuity

Distant vision was measured by a standard Snellen chart (Annexure 5) having Bangla alphabet, this board consists of high contrast letters decreasing in size from top to the bottom row. Each row is denoted by a number from 6 to 60, which corresponds to the distance from which a normal eye, i.e., the one without refractive errors, could read from the denoted distance. The chart was placed such that the 4th line (6/18) of the chart is at the eye level of the student on a wall which had adequate illumination. The child was seated 3metres (10 feet) away from the board and told to sit up straight and each eye was tested separately by asking him/her to cover the other eye softly with the palm of their ipsilateral hand and asked to read down to the lowest row of letters that they can see clearly. Care was taken to ensure the occluded eye wasn't pressed and the tested eye was observed to prevent squeezing/squinting (pinhole effective) while reading the chart. For those who already wear spectacles, the aided was measured at first, followed by the measurement of unaided visual acuity. If a child could read up to 6/6, it was considered normal. If a person couldn't read any lines, finger counting was done from a distance of 3feet followed by 1feet. Failing hand movement from 3feet followed by 1feet was done. Near vision was measured by having the student read a newsprint/a book from a distance of 14 inches.

Color vision

The Ishihara test consists of a book of plates with a circle of dots that form a random number of figures. These figures will be visible to those with normal color vision but not those with red-green defects. The student will be seated in an adequately lit room, the test plate held at a distance of 75 cm from the student's eye. The examiner will flick through each plate giving a 5second delay between each plate and the student is asked to read the numbers on the Ishihara color plates which are matched with the reference list to check for any deficiency.

Pupillary examination

It included assessment of the size, shape, regularity, and equality of the pupils of the left and right eyes and the pupillary reactions as the student focused on a distant object. The pupil is centrally located in the iris, and is round and regular and both pupils are equal in size and shape. Pupillary light reflex was tested in a dimly lit room, the student was instructed not to look at the light source but rather to look at a distant point/object. The pen torch was positioned from just below and the light was slowly shining into their eyes. In the direct reflex, rapid constriction of the ipsilateral pupil occurs when a light source is introduced, which returns to the original size when the light source is removed, and in consensual reflex

both pupils should constrict at the same time when the light source is shone on one eye with a hand placed on the bridge of the nose so that light doesn't pass to the opposite eye. For the accommodation reflex, the student was asked to fixate on a pen placed at an arm's length away (the distant object dilating pupil) and then told to look at the pen while it was brought close to his/her nose, the eyes converge and if normal, both pupils should constrict and then dilate again when a distant gaze was resumed.

Visual Fields

Visual fields were checked by Confrontation test, which relied on comparing the student's visual field with the researchers own. The researcher sat 1metre away from the student and faced the student at his/her eye level. The student was told to cover one eye and the researcher covered her same eye (i.e., contralateral eye). The student was asked to look into the eyes of the researcher while the researcher held a red pin right outside the outer limits of her temporal field. The pin was moved slowly from the peripheral field towards the center of the student's vision and the student was asked to say when he/she first saw the pin and it was repeated for each of the 4 visual quadrants. The test was then repeated for the other eye.

Extraocular movements

Extraocular movements were tested by seating the students 3 feet away from the researcher. The students head was steadied by gently placing a hand under their chin and she/he was asked to focus and follow the moving index finger with their eyes without moving their head and the gaze was checked in six cardinal directions by tracing an imaginary 'H' shape and looking at how both eyes moved. Presence of any nystagmus was checked and the question about any diplopia when looking in any particular way was asked.

Basic and other eye examinations

At first, external eye examination was done to see any obvious abnormalities, i.e., exophthalmos, enophthalmos, ptosis, blinking, watering, discharge, etc. It included inspection of the lid, lashes and its surrounding tissues (stye, chalazion, blepharitis, etc.), the student was asked to look up as both lower lids were depressed with the researcher thumb to inspect the color and vascular pattern of the conjunctiva (congestion) and sclera (pallor, redness or yellowing), Cornea is normally translucent, smooth and avascular (ulceration, scar, opacity) and the lens (cataract), is transparent with uniform in density. To check for strabismus in young people, Hirschberg corneal reflex test were done. Light of the pen-torch was focused on the bridge of the nose of the student and he/she was asked to fixate on the point light held at a distance of 33cm and symmetry of the corneal light reflection from the center of the pupil was noted. If the reflex was symmetrical in both eyes, then strabismus was said to be absent, but if it was asymmetrical then deviation was said to be present in the squinting eye. Depth of the anterior chamber was seen by shining tangential light (from the temporal canthus such that the pen torch lies in the same plane of the eye) to the cornea and assessing whether the researcher was able to see the entire iris without a shadow. Normally the anterior chamber is clear of aqueous humor and deep, and the iris lies flat while the whole iris is illuminated, but in case of a very shallow anterior chamber the iris lies forward, blocking some of the light and very little of the iris is illuminated.

Height

Height was measured by a measuring tape in a standing position. The respondent was asked to stand on a wall looking straight ahead. The back of the head, shoulder blades, buttocks, and the heels touched the wall, heels together, and toes were apart. Then height was recorded in centimeters.

Weight

Weight was measured by a weighing the scale placed on a plane surface and the respondent stood in the center of the scale platform facing the researcher hands at sides, and looking straight ahead. Before measuring the weight, of unnecessary clothes, shoes were removed from the respondent. Respondents were also asked to empty their bladder before measuring weight. The weight of the respondents was measured in kilograms.

Data processing

After data collection, the questionnaires were thoroughly checked and verified for consistency and completeness. Variables were defined using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 and the data were entered, cleaned, and edited and new variables constructed or recoded as per requirements of the analysis. Missing data were checked through a frequency runs. Distribution of all quantitative continuous data was checked, if the variable/data was not normally distributed, log transformation was done for further analysis. An analysis plan was developed according to the objectives of the study.

Data analysis

Descriptive analysis: Descriptive analysis of the data included frequencies and percentages and were shown as comparative charts. Socio-demographic and economic data, lifestyle data, and data of symptoms of visual problems were presented in tables. Only continuous data, age, was shown by histogram. Sex, religion, and data regarding the schools were depicted by pie and bar diagrams.

Inferential analysis: Inferential analysis was done according to the objectives of the study. The dependent variables of the study were 'diminished visual acuity' and 'ocular morbidity' which were both categorical variables. When both dependent and independent variables were categorical, Pearson Chi Square test was done. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$. Binary logistic regression was done using categorical and continuous independent variables with binary dependent variables. The results were presented in tables and graphs.

Ethical consideration

An English version of the informed written consent and assent form was drafted and then translated into Bengali to take consent from the respondents. Data were collected by face-to-face interview using the Bengali version of the semi structured questionnaire. Ethical approval for the study was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of NIPSOM. Permission was taken from the Program manager of the School Health Program, Civil Surgeons of both Dhaka and Chittagong cities and from the respective school authorities. Before starting the interview, the respondents were informed about the objectives, purpose, and procedure of the study. Respondents were assured about the confidentiality of the data. Their name, phone number, or anything which could identify them would not be published or exposed anywhere. Risk and benefits were also explained clearly to the respondents. They were informed about the full right to participate or to refuse and withdraw from this study at any stage or time. No invasive procedures or interventions were given in this study. No sensitive or personal questions were asked. Respondents were assured that there would be no harm to them or their children during the study and that none of the Child Rights' will be violated. Privacy was maintained properly during the interview of each respondent. All of their enquiries were clarified. A copy of informed written consent and assent form was provided to all the respondents. Data were collected only from those respondents who participated voluntarily. Their participation and contribution is acknowledged with due respect.

Limitations of the study

Some limitations were encountered while conducting the study that may have influenced the quality of the study to some extent.

1. The study was conducted in two cities of Bangladesh, Dhaka, and Chittagong, so the findings of the study merely represent the whole child population of Bangladesh.
2. Convenient sampling technique was applied to select the four schools in this study, which may have resulted in some selection bias.
3. Cross-sectional study was done so the prevalence of some of the ocular morbidity may be understated as the child may not have been suffering at that moment.
4. There might have some recall bias as some information was self-reported by the respondents and their guardians.
5. Although Log MAR chart is the best option for Visual Acuity test, in this study Snellen chart was used as it is recommended by most of the ophthalmologists in the eye hospitals of Bangladesh.
6. Cycloplegic refraction of children with visual impairment could not be done due to lack of resources, so a number of undiagnosed cases may be dropped out among these students.
7. Some measurement bias may occur as the basic eye examination was dependent on the perception of the researcher and not done using ophthalmic instruments or by an ophthalmologist.
8. The time that was scheduled for data collection unfortunately coincided with the exam schedules and religious vacations, so it was quite difficult for the researcher to reach the students and their guardians, who were willing to participate in the interviews. Therefore, in spite of maximum effort by the researcher, 277 samples could finally be enrolled.

RESULTS

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted on 277 children of class 1 to class 5 from four selected primary schools of two different cities, to see if there is any difference between visual problems in students of the schools under the School Health Program and those that are not. Among the study places, a total of 135 students were selected from the two program (SHP) schools, Bagmonirum A.S. Government Primary School, Dampara, Chittagong and Hazi Gani Government Primary School, Azimpur, Dhaka. The two non-program (non-SHP) schools were CDA Shishu Kanon School, Mehdibag, Chittagong, and Nilkhet Government Primary School, Dhaka, and a total of 142 students were enrolled from these two schools. The collected data were cleaned, edited, and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The analyzed data are presented in this chapter through tables and graphs. The findings of the study are described under the following sections:

1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the students
2. Information regarding the schools of the respondents
3. Family background of the students
4. Risk factors related to visual problems
5. Symptoms related to visual problems

1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents:

Data were collected on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents including age, sex, religion, and level of education of the students.

Figure 1: Distribution of the respondents by their age

Figure 2: Distribution of the respondents by their sex

Figure 3: Distribution of non-SHP and SHP students by religion

Figure 4: Distribution of the respondents by their level of education

2. Information regarding the schools of the respondents:

Four primary schools, two SHP and two non-SHP schools, were selected from two cities of Bangladesh, two schools of Dhaka, and two schools of Chittagong. The highest number of participants were from the SHP school of Chittagong (27.1%), Bagmonirum A. S. Government Primary School, Dampara, followed by the non-SHP schools of Dhaka (26.0%), Nilkhet Government Primary School, and Chittagong (25.3%), CDA Shishu Kanon School, Mehedibagh and the lowest from the SHP school of Dhaka (21.7%), Hazi Gani Government Primary School, Azimpur. Among these schools, CDA Shishu Kanon School was the only Non - Government school (25.3%) and the other three were Government Schools (74.7%). More than half of the respondents were from Chittagong (52.3%) and the rest (47.7%) were from Dhaka. (Fig 5)

Figure 5: Distribution of the respondents by the type of schools

It was seen that health education was given in the schools and first aid was available but there were no health cards for individual students and there were no school-based health centers. After first aid was given, the students were referred to the doctor. Those under SHP referred the patients to the School Health Clinics where, according to need, they were treated or referred to the hospital. There was proper sanitation facilities and safe drinking water supply in the schools. The safe drinking water supply was from different sources for the four schools. Hazi Gani government primary school, Azimpur, Dhaka, supplied tap water which was filtered water from WASHA. The filter set up in the roof of the school building was given to them by the NGO ‘Sajeda foundation’. Nilkhet Government primary school supplied tap water from the Dhaka University pipeline which was safe for drinking. Bagmonirum A. S. Government primary school supplied water from a deep tube well which

was installed in the school premises by the Chittagong City Corporation. CDA Shishu Kanan School supplied water from a deep tube well which was installed in the school premises by the CDA officers association for the kids going to that school.

3. Family Background of the students:

Information regarding the level of education and occupation of the parents, family type, number of family members, average monthly income, type of housing, etc. were collected.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants parents

Socio-demographic characteristics	All schools (n = 277) f (%)	Non-SHP schools (n = 142) f (%)	SHP school (n = 135) f (%)
Level of education of the Mother			
Illiterate	8 (2.9)	1 (0.7)	7 (5.2)
Can sign name only	15 (5.4)	5 (3.5)	10 (7.4)
Upton primary level	112 (40.4)	55 (38.7)	57 (42.2)
Upton secondary level	89 (32.1)	53 (37.3)	36 (26.7)
Higher secondary	31 (11.2)	12 (8.5)	19 (14.1)
Graduation	19 (6.9)	13 (9.2)	6 (4.4)
Post-graduation	3 (1.1)	3 (2.1)	0 (0)
Occupation of the Mother			
Housewife	233 (84.1)	118 (83.1)	115 (85.2)
Service	40 (14.4)	21 (14.8)	19 (14.1)
Business	4 (1.4)	3 (2.1)	1 (0.7)
Level of education of Father			
Illiterate	7 (2.5)	1 (0.7)	6 (4.4)
Can sign name only	6 (2.2)	3 (2.1)	3 (2.2)
Upton primary level	85 (30.7)	47 (33.1)	38 (28.1)
Upton secondary level	90 (32.5)	38 (26.8)	52 (38.5)
Higher secondary	28 (10.1)	11 (7.7)	17 (12.6)
Graduation	51 (18.4)	32 (22.5)	19 (14.1)
Post-graduation	10 (3.6)	10 (7.0)	0 (0)
Occupation of Father			
Business	83 (30.0)	39 (27.5)	44 (32.6)
Service	169 (61.0)	89 (62.7)	80 (59.3)
Other occupations	23 (8.3)	14 (9.9)	9 (6.7)

Family income:

Table 2: Average monthly family income

Average Monthly Income (in taka)	All schools (n = 277) f (%)	Non-SHP schools (n = 142) f (%)	SHP schools (n = 135) f (%)
Below 10000	50 (18.1)	11 (7.7)	39 (28.9)
10000 to 20000	91 (32.9)	41 (28.9)	50 (37.0)
20000 to 30000	68 (24.5)	38 (26.8)	30 (22.2)
Above 30000	68 (24.5)	52 (36.6)	16 (11.9)
Range (in taka)	2000 to 200000	2000 to 200000	3000 to 100000
Mean ± s.d. (in taka)	30830.29 ± 28407.19	39742.96 ± 34547.672	21242.42 ± 14775.35

Type and size of the respondent’s family:

Figure 6: Distribution of respondents by family type

Type of house the student lives in:

Figure 7: Distribution of the respondents by type of housing facilities

4. Risk factors for visual problems

Information regarding vaccination

The EPI coverage was found to be quite high, showing that 97.1% students had completed their vaccination but about 1.4% of the students reported of not being given vaccines at all and 1.4% had not completed their EPI schedule. 10.1% of the respondents said they gave other vaccines which were vaccine for Hepatitis B, Rotavirus, Tetanus, Toxoid, and Pneumococcal vaccine. Nearly half of the respondents (48%) had taken anti-helminthic medication every 6months followed by two-fifths of the respondents who took it every 3months, a mere 9.4% took it once a year and about 4.7% reported of never having taken it. As to the EPI schedule, 96.4% of the respondents said that they had given their children Vitamin A supplementation from 6months up to 6years of age. 1.8% of the respondents said they did not partake in the vitamin A plus campaign and 1.8% said they don’t remember. About three-fifths of the respondents (59.6%) said the mothers were given Vitamin A supplementation within 42days of giving birth, while nearly two-fifths (36.1%) of them said they weren’t given supplementation and a few (4.3%) said they couldn’t recall. Three-fifths of the respondents (61%) said their children breastfed for more than 2years, while about one-third (27.1%) they breastfed from 6month to less than 2years.

Information regarding lifestyle

Lifestyle information included weekly intake, of Vitamin A containing foods, questions about maintaining ocular hygiene, i.e., wiping eyes with dirty hands or cloth, using cosmetics (surma, kajol, eyeliner), using sunglasses, playing (indoors or outdoors). About half the respondents (48%) said they rubbed their eyes with a dirty hands or cloth while the rest did not. One-third of the respondents used a type of cosmetics (32.9%), and only 15.5% said they wore sunglasses. Only 2.5% of the respondents said that they did not play any indoor or outdoor games. Amongst the rest, about one-third reported of playing outdoors (28.9%), indoors (33.2%) and 35.4% said they played both indoor and outdoor games.

Table 3: Weekly Consumption of Vitamin A containing food by the respondent

Food items and their intake by the respondents during last week	All schools (n = 277) f (%)
Colored vegetables (carrot, spinach, pumpkin, sweet potato)	
Not at all	31 (11.2)
3days or less	119 (43)
4days or more	105 (37.9)
Infrequently	22 (7.9)
Colored Fruits (ripe guava, ripe mango, banana)	
Not at all	0 (0.0)
3days or less	139 (50.2)
4days or more	122 (44)
Infrequently	16 (5.8)
Egg yolk	
Not at all	28 (10.1)
3days or less	120 (43.3)
4days or more	129 (46.6)
Infrequently	0 (0.0)
Milk and dairy products (cheese, butter)	
Not at all	83 (30.0)
3days or less	127 (45.8)
4days or more	67 (24.4)
Infrequently	0 (0.0)
Small fish (mola, dhela, kachki)	
Not at all	129 (46.6)
3days or less	59 (21.3)
4days or more	8 (2.9)
Infrequently	81 (29.2)
Liver	
Not at all	90 (32.5)
3days or less	37 (13.4)
4days or more	0 (0.0)
Infrequently	150 (54.2)

Information regarding Eye Strain

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by different eye straining activities

Daily eye straining activities (in hours)	Schools	Students f (%)	Range (in hours)	Mean (in hours)	Standard deviation
Study time (after school hours)	Non-SHP	142 (100)	1.0 to 6.0	2.66	± 1.22
	SHP	135 (100)	0.5 to 6.0	2.75	± 1.28
	Total	277 (100)	0.5 to 6.0	2.70	± 1.25
Watching TV	Non-SHP	127 (89.4)	0.5 to 6.0	1.85	± 1.39
	SHP	128 (94.8)	0.5 to 6.0	2.09	± 1.43
	Total	255 (92.1)	0.5 to 6.0	1.97	± 1.41
Using Computer	Non-SHP	16 (11.3)	0.5 to 2.0	0.13	± 0.40
	SHP	3 (2.2)	1.0 to 2.0	0.03	± 0.21
	Total	19 (6.9)	0.5 to 2.0	0.08	± 0.33
Using Mobile	Non-SHP	97 (68.3)	0.5 to 5.0	0.73	± 0.78
	SHP	62 (45.9)	0.5 to 6.0	0.63	± 1.04
	Total	159 (57.4)	0.5 to 6.0	0.68	± 0.92

Information regarding known visual problems

Among the 277 respondents, only 27 students (9.7%) reported of having felt visual problems from an age of 5 years to 11 years, the mean age was 7.96 ± 1.63 years. Nearly half (48.1%) were from non-SHP schools and a little more than half (51.9%) were from SHP schools. Of whom, only 16 students (59.3%) visited the eye specialist and 11 students (40.7%) did not. The mean age at which they visited the doctor was 7.87 ± 1.64 years. Among these 16 students, 11 students (68.8%) wore spectacles, and only 2 students (18.2%) reported of change in spectacle power, while 9 students (81.8%) reported no change over the past year. About two-thirds of the students (62.5%) had their prescription and one-third of the students (37.5%) had lost it. Of the 10 students who had their prescription, 7 students wore spectacles, among whom 2 were myopic (- power) and 5 were hypermetropic (+ power). About 20 students (7.2%) gave a history of accidental eye injury, mostly while playing or by falling down, commonly in the left eye (4%), followed by the right eye (2.9%) and both eyes (0.4%). There were no histories of ocular surgery in any student.

Figure 8: Distribution of the respondents with known visual problems

Symptoms checklist

Table 5: Symptoms related to visual problems

Symptoms	All schools n (%)
Difficulty in Near vision	
No	264 (95.3%)
Left eye	3 (1.1)
Right eye	1 (0.4)
Both eyes	9 (3.2)
Difficulty in Far vision	
No	220 (79.4)
Left eye	18 (6.5)
Right eye	9 (3.2)
Both eyes	30 (10.8)
Difficulty in Both near and far	
No	275 (99.3)
Left eye	2 (0.7)
Right eye	1 (0.4)
Both eyes	3 (1.1)
Double vision	

No	275 (99.3)
Left eye	2 (0.7)
h/o Conjunctivitis	
No	239 (86.3)
Left eye	15 (5.4)
Right eye	5 (1.8)
Both eyes	18 (6.5)
h/o Conjunctival congestion	
No	277 (100)
h/o Blepharitis	
No	235 (84.8)
Left eye	9 (3.2)
Right eye	17 (6.1)
Both eyes	16 (5.8)
h/o Stye/chalazion	
No	251 (90.6)
Left eye	16 (5.8)
Right eye	7 (2.5)
Both eyes	3 (1.1)
h/o Eye watering	
No	220 (79.4)

Left eye	14 (5.1)
Right eye	13 (4.7)
Both eyes	30 (10.8)
h/o Discharge	
No	272 (98.2)
Left eye	2 (0.7)
Right eye	1 (0.4)
Both eyes	2 (0.7)
h/o Eyeache	
No	246 (88.8)
Left eye	9 (3.2)
Right eye	9 (3.2)
Both eyes	13 (4.7)
h/o Burning eye	
No	255 (92.1)
Left eye	10 (3.6)
Right eye	4 (1.4)
Both eyes	8 (2.9)
h/o Photophobia	
No	202 (72.9)
Left eye	8 (2.9)
Right eye	5 (1.8)
Both eyes	62 (22.4)
h/o Frowning	
No	269 (97.1)
Left eye	2 (0.7)
Both eyes	6 (2.2)
h/o Squint	
No	274 (98.9)

Left eye	2 (0.7)
Both eyes	1 (0.4)
h/o Color blindness	
No	275 (99.3)
Yes	2 (0.7)
h/o Night blindness	
No	274 (98.9)
Yes	3 (1.1)
h/o Headache	
No	129 (46.6)
yes	148 (53.4)
h/o Allergic condition / Asthma	
No	205 (74.0)
yes	72 (26.0)
h/o Chronic oral steroid intake	
No	0 (0)

Family history of eye problems

Table 6: Family history of spectacle use

Those who wear spectacles (Relation with child)	All schools n (%)
Mother	43 (15.5)
Father	68 (24.5)
Sibling	40 (14.4)
Paternal family	98 (35.4)
Maternal family	112 (40.4)

5. Symptoms related to visual problems

Visual Acuity

Figure 9: Distribution of the respondents by diminished vision

Color vision

Figure 10: Distribution of the respondents by color vision

Pupil

Pupils of all students were checked with a pen torch and found to be round and regular in shape and reacted to light. Consensual light reflex was seen and was present for all students. Pupil size was equal in both eyes.

There were no other abnormalities of the pupil (no white pupil)

Squint

Strabismus was seen by Hirschberg Corneal Reflex Test.

Figure 11: Distribution of the respondents by squint (left eye)

Eye Watering

Figure 12: Distribution of the respondents by reflex eye watering

Cornea

There was no corneal dryness or opacity.

Conjunctiva

There was no conjunctivitis or conjunctival congestion.

Lens

No cataract.

Eyelids

Figure 13: Distribution of respondents by lid infection

Other Ocular problems

No other problems.

Table 7: Prevalence of ocular morbidity by socio demographic characteristics

Demographic data	All schools (n = 277) f (%)	statistic (X ²) (p value)
Age		
Below 10years	74 (57.4)	X ² = 0.16 p = 0.901
10years and above	55 (42.6)	
Sex		
Male	66 (49.3%)	X ² = 0.751 p = 0.386
Female	63 (44.1%)	
Religion		
Islam	108 (83.7)	X ² = 0.966 p = 0.326
Others	21 (16.3)	
Mother's education		
Illiterate	11 (8.5)	X ² = 2.239 p = 0.692
Up to primary	54 (41.9)	
Up to secondary	41 (31.8)	
Higher secondary	11 (8.5)	
Graduation and above	12 (9.3)	
Mother's occupation		
Housewife	112 (86.8)	X ² = 1.323 p = 0.250
Working	17 (13.2)	
Father's education		
Illiterate	5 (3.9)	X ² = 0.798 p = 0.939
Up to primary	41 (31.8)	
Up to secondary	41 (31.8)	

Higher secondary	12 (9.3)	
Graduation and above	30 (23.3)	
Father's occupation		
Business	34 (26.4)	$X^2 = 2.425$
Service	85 (65.9)	$p = 0.297$
Others	10 (7.8)	
Type of family		
Nuclear	91 (70.5)	$X^2 = 0.495$
Joint	38 (29.5)	$p = 0.482$
Average monthly family income (BDT)		
Below 10000	25 (19.4)	
10100 - 20000	41 (31.8)	$X^2 = 1.772$
20100 - 30000	28 (21.7)	$p = 0.621$
Above 30000	35 (27.1)	

Table 8: Effect of eye straining activity on ocular morbidity

Eye training activities	All schools (n = 277) n (%)	Test statistic (X^2) (p value)
Study time (after school hours)		
Less than 2 hours	60 (46.5)	0.392
2 - 4 hours	57 (44.2)	$p = 0.822$
More than 4 hours	12 (9.3)	
Type of light in study room		
Insufficient light	7 (5.4)	0.698
Sufficient light	122 (94.6)	$p = 0.404$
Watching TV		
Doesn't use	10 (7.8)	0.878
Less than 2 hours	81 (62.8)	$p = 0.645$
More than 2 hours	38 (29.5)	
TV distance		
Near distance	25 (21)	0.427
Moderate distance	73 (61.3)	$p = 0.808$
Quite far	21 (17.6)	
Using Computer		
Doesn't use	121 (93.8)	0.163
0.5 - 2 hours	8 (6.2)	$p = 0.686$
Using Mobile		
Doesn't use	60 (46.5)	1.583
Less than 2 hours	62 (48.1)	$p = 0.453$
More than 2 hours	7 (5.4)	
Total screen time		
No screen time	2 (1.6)	3.432
Less than 2 hours	64 (49.6)	$p = 0.330$
2 - 4 hours	44 (34.1)	
More than 4 hours	19 (14.7)	

Table 9: Effect of nutritional status on ocular morbidity

Ocular morbidity in students	f (%)	Test statistic (X^2) (p value)
with Stunting		
All schools (n = 277)	9 (50%)	$X^2 = 0.91$ ($p = 0.763$)
Non - SHP schools (n = 142)	6 (85.7%)	$X^2 = 4.556$ ($p = 0.033$)
SHP schools (n = 135)	3 (27.3%)	$X^2 = 1.810$ ($p = 0.179$)

From the above table, it can be seen that, although the values aren't significant for all schools and SHP schools, the Chi square test is significant for Non-SHP schools ($p = 0.033$)

showing there is a weak association between ocular morbidity in malnourished students of non-program schools.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study was conducted with a view to determine if there is any difference among students studying in schools under the School Health Program (SHP) and schools that are not under the program. The primary school children and their guardians were taken as respondents from two SHP schools and two non-SHP schools. No such comparative study regarding the School Health Program was revealed during the literature review. According to the literature review, most of the previous studies were carried out focusing on the epidemiological pattern of ocular morbidity in children. Very few studies were carried out specifically on primary school children. Most of the studies were population based with a large sample size.

In Bangladesh, large-scale population-based study was carried out 2011 in rural and urban schools of Narayanganj, A total of 4,625 children were screened, aged 6-15years. Out of them 67% were boys and the rest 33% were girls. Ocular morbidity (refractory error) was found in 9.5 % children out of which 4.43% were boys and 5.06% were girls. (Rahman, M. M., 2014), This study was used as the baseline for the current study. Other studies in Bangladesh included data obtained from a community level pediatric vision screening, camp, age group 5-15 years, in two sub districts of Khulna in 2001- 2002, in which the prevalence of refractive error was found to be 1%, with female predominance. (Raihan, A. 2005)

In this study, the students of class 1 to class 5 were found to be of age 6 to 13years. The mean age of the participants observed were (9.01 ± 1.84) years, with more female participation (53.3%). Diminished visual acuity was found in 36.8% of the respondents, the proportion being more in non-program school students (19.9%) than students studying in program schools (17%), which is quite higher than the above studies which occurred earlier in Bangladesh. Color blindness was found in 2.6% of the respondents, of which 0.4% was total color blind and 2.2% were Red-Green color deficient, and was equally distributed (1.1%) among program and non-program schools. Style was found in 0.8% of the respondents who were from SHP schools. Reflex watering occurred in 18.8% of the students, 13.7% from non-SHP schools, and 5.1% from SHP schools. No other ocular morbidities were found during this study time frame. In non-program school students, a significant association was seen between malnourishment and ocular morbidity ($p = 0.033$). In a study of refractive errors among primary school children that occurred in Egypt, the screening revealed that 116 students out of 480 (24%) had refractive errors. Of them, 22% patients had myopia and only 2% had hyperopia. The patients were found to be affected by watching television for long durations, in dim or yellow light, and at a distance less than the healthy recommended level. (Elkot, M.M., 2017)

Conclusion

The comparative cross-sectional study occurred in four primary schools of Dhaka and Chittagong with a view to determine how the distribution and prevalence of visual problems in students of class 1 to class 5 aged 6 to 13years, varied from schools under School Health Program (SHP) to non-SHP schools. From the results and discussion, it was found that diminished vision was more common in non-SHP students, age group below 10years, and more propensity towards males. Chi square test was done to test the association. Most variables, such as age, sex, religion, family background, eye straining activities, etc., most of which was not significant. This study revealed that ocular morbidity was weakly associated

with malnourished non-SHP students. Researchers tried to emphasize on the risk factors related to visual problems in this study, and some positive relations and associations may come out for which different types of study are warranted in the future. This small-scale study may not precisely reflect the actual scenario, but it may generate a guideline for further research in this field and will give the concerned authorities valid and reliable data for making plans and policies for cost-effective school eye screening programs to be implemented in schools all over the country regardless of it being a government or non-government school as the school is an important platform for promoting the health of its students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the recommendations with a view to decreasing the prevalence of uncorrected and untreated visual problems in childhood:

1. This school-based study was conducted on very few and selected urban primary schools, so a further community-based survey should be organized on a large scale, in all districts of the country covering all age groups to include preschool and high school students of both urban and rural settings, including all types of schools, i.e., government, non-government, NGO, city corporation, madrasa, English medium etc., thus also covering all socioeconomic strata.
2. From a public health perspective, basic vision screening is an appropriate strategy to reduce refractive errors, for which the treatment is simple, effective, and inexpensive. It should be done for all students to be newly enrolled in the primary school level and then followed up on a yearly basis.
3. Awareness about the serious impact of undetected and uncorrected visual problems should be made in classrooms, school meetings, and programs. People's consciousness about spectacles should be increased, spectacles are needed not only to supplement for diminished vision in the elderly, but also essential for children and adolescents to support and correct their sight, they should know that ignoring minor or temporary difficulties may lead to further and more severe impairments including gradual blindness.
4. Factual implementation of the School Health Program in schools should have had a more visible impact on the findings of visual health of SHP students, the authority concerned should take initiatives to regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of these screening programs for further improvement.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am grateful to Almighty Allah, the most Gracious and most Merciful, for enabling me to complete this research work. My best regard and humble admiration to the Director, National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), Mohakhali, Dhaka, for her whole hearted support in the conduction of different aspects of the study. My sincere and heartiest thanks to all faculty members of Department of Health Education, National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), Mohakhali, Dhaka, for their guidance, sincere suggestions and cooperation during performing this work. I also wish to acknowledge for excellent help and assistance from my colleagues. Finally, I want to thank the participants of the study for their excellent help in data collection.

Conflict of Interest:

There was no competing or conflict of interest for this study.

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Cite this article:

Md. Shahariar Islam (2021). Visual problems in Students of Schools under the School Health Program and Others. *Journal of Scientific Reports*, 3(1), 26-50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4718485>

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